

Newsletter
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In this Issue

The CONSENTIS architecture at-a-glance	Page 1
Synergy with the MyHealth@MyHands project	Page 1
2nd General Assembly Meeting in Tilburg	Page 1
Technical Meeting in Athens	Page 2
CONSENTIS Project Presentation	Page 2

Identity and Consent Management for EU Digital and Data Strategies

| The CONSENTIS architecture at-a-glance

CONSENTIS innovates by using a Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) framework as a foundational layer to achieve GDPR-compliant consent management. At its core sits the SSI "Trust Triangle" clearly delineating roles and interactions among Issuers (CMP as an SSI Issuer Agent), SSI Holders (data subjects/users managing their identity and consents through wallets), and SSI Verifiers (entities validating consent before data access, e.g. medical entities such as doctors, clinics, NHRs). A wallet-centric trust layer hands control of personal data to users. Each user holds "consent tokens" (CTs) formatted as verifiable credentials (VC) in their wallet; healthcare providers, insurers and third parties interact with those credentials through standard SSI flows. Surrounding these SSI interactions are CMP (consent management platform) agents that interface with the SSI to broker data access. When a relying party requests information, the CMP checks for a consent token in real time and grants or denies access based on its status.

CONSENTIS employs Hyperledger Aries with a permissioned Fabric ledger (blockchain) alongside W3C-standardized DIDs and VCs. This ensures end-users maintain sovereignty over their identity and consent decisions. This approach not only meets regulatory compliance by embedding privacy-by-design principles but also aligns with project objectives which explicitly emphasize using SSI for consent management.

| CONSENTIS explores synergy with the MyHealth@MyHands project

CONSENTIS recently presented its architecture and consent data model to the [myHealth@myHands](#) EU project, exploring a synergy between the two initiatives.

It focuses on a common compliant consent record model, enabling consent-driven data sharing across secondary healthcare data usage scenarios; and examines how EUDI Wallet-interoperable VC formats might support consent issuance, presentation and verification. The discussion also opened pathways for joint work on eIDAS-aligned digital consent lifecycle management, marking an exchange of knowledge, standards and technical approaches benefiting EU digital health ecosystems.

| 2nd General Assembly Meeting in Tilburg

On October 14-15, 2025, the 2nd General Assembly meeting of CONSENTIS was successfully held in Tilburg, hosted by TIU. The meeting covered several technical management activities, including the analysis of CONSENTIS technologies, the framework design developed in WP3, and the building blocks and underlying technologies implemented in WP4 and WP5. Key results that were described in D3.1 and D3.2 were presented. In addition, the partners discussed plans for core component delivery (Wallet, CMP agents/UI, Blockchain, SSI trust layer, Data Audit, Risk Assessment), supported by concrete sprint-based milestones scheduled up to M18. The partners agreed on specific technical achievements to be reached by M18, aligned with the project's technical KPIs and objectives. A detailed development plan, including sprint structure and GitHub workflows, was also reviewed.

| Technical Meeting in Athens

On November 13, 2025, the technical meeting of CONSENTIS was successfully held in Athens, hosted by Aegis. All partners presented their key offerings and targeted achievements, identifying technical blockers, dependencies, and open technical issues. A long discussion followed on the architecture integration points, leading to a refinement of the logical architecture diagram and its associated flows.

| CONSENTIS Project Presentation at SEEDA-CECNSM 2025

UPAT represented the CONSENTIS consortium at the 10th South-East Europe Design Automation, Computer Engineering, Computer Networks and Social Media Conference (SEEDA-CECNSM 2025), delivering the presentation titled “An Innovative Framework for Identity and Consent Management for EU Digital and Data Strategies, CONSENTIS.” The conference took place in Patras, Greece, from 19 to 21 September.

NEXT PLENARY MEETING
TO BE HELD FEBROURY 2026
IN ATHENS GREECE
HOSTED BY KARAVIAS

JOIN US IN SHAPING THE FUTURE OF DIGITAL IDENTITY!

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